

EXAMINATION OF SOCIAL MEDIA USING INDIVIDUALS' RECREATION TENDENCIES

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Abstract:

Nowadays, there has been an increasing count of actively social media using individuals. This new kind of media which is used by most of the population can generate an impact on users' tendencies. Recreation activities increase individuals' quality of life and provide them some physical, social, and psychological benefits. Individual's participation to these recreation activities facilitate development primarily to the participant himself and then to the society. In this context, this study is an examination of active recreation tendencies on social media using individuals. It was conducted with 379 participants who studies at Higher Education in Sports. In order to measure social media users' active recreation tendencies, a questionnaire based on the Recreational Exercise Motivation Measure which has the reliability and validity of Turkish version made by Gurbuz, Asci and Celebi (2006) and originally developed by Rogers and Morris (2003) and the Facebook Intensity Scale developed by Ellison, Steinfield and Lampe (2010) were prepared and used. According to Cronbach Alpha ($\alpha=0,878$) the questionnaire found reliable. In order to analyze the results besides descriptive statistics of socio-demographics, the questionnaire was factor analyzed and three dimensions as physical, social and psychological tendency are obtained. Mann Whitney U and Kruskal Wallis tests are used to determine whether there are any significant differences.

Keywords: media, recreation, Facebook, active participation

Introduction

Some of social media tools have reached one billion active users on August 2015. (<https://www.facebook.com/facebook/info?tab=milestone>). Individuals can connect these tools at any time and place they want by means of an internet connection through their smartphones and tablets without using any computer.

According to Robinson (2011) when people are on the computer in their free time for activity, the time spent on their other free time activity decreases. Nowadays it is possible to do almost everything through smart devices. Therefore, without the need of being on computer all day people can take these devices with them to all places.

A study by Kramer, Guillory and Hancock (2014) (on 689,003 people) about Facebook which has the most user count in the world and Turkey helps to explain how people's judgments are affected by this social networking site. The results showed that according to news' status of being positive or negative on their main pages can manipulate the contents they share about themselves. It is suggested that people who interact with positive sharing also share positive content about themselves, and likely who interact with negative sharing, share negative content about themselves.

Social media is a system which people affect and also be affected by each other. Some of studies showed that 25% of search results on internet about any brand consist of content links made by users, 34% consist of bloggers' opinion about the product or brand (Kara, 2012; Wautera, 2010). In that case, we confront the importance and the position of social media for the process of evaluation on services that people get. During the recent years, researchers tend towards to social media marketing because of the possibility to steer the consumption behavior by social media. This concept generally concentrates on the importance of consumer buying behavior. The concentration on the recreation field should be not just on the importance of buying an activity it should also be on experiencing or benefiting from public recreation opportunities. In order to concentrate on these areas the tendency and interests to recreation activities should be identified.

Literature Review

At literature review, the term recreation comes from any activity pursued during leisure time. Leisure time shortly includes free, non-obligatory time and it is characterized as a type of freedom (Demir N. & Demir C., 2006, s.37). According to Zorba (2007), leisure time has three main functions which are resting, amusement and self-improvement. When it comes to the action of gaining functions, the term recreation arises. At Turkish Language Instruction Contemporary Turkish Dictionary, the word recreation means

activities which people participate voluntarily for sport and amusement in their free time. Thus, various activities which people act upon their free will after performing their obligatory needs are called as recreation.

Karaküçük (2005) defines recreation as relaxing, amusing activities joined by individuals or group when Kılbaş (2004) as activities or experiences individuals join in their free time to get pleasure or to gain some physical, social or emotional behaviors. As to Stebbins (2005) recreation means activities that are providing individual satisfaction and a chance to use his own capabilities and skills which individual joins willingly in his free time and without an obligation. Similarly Cordes and Ibrahim (1999) consider recreation as all meaningful and amusing activities to individuals which they voluntarily participate in their free time.

Basic needs to recreation and benefits from it can be gathered generally to three topics Physical, Social, Psychological (Sevil, Şimşek, Katırcı, Çelik and Çeliksoy, 2012; Kaba, 2009; Torkildsen, 2005). Fitness is the main factor of a healthy living and leisure activities. It is divided into two as health related and skill related factors. Skill related factors involve factors like coordination, balance, as health related factors involve factors like cardiovascular capacity, strength, flexibility, and body composition (Kaba, 2009). Recreation activities, especially active recreation activities increase fitness because of the structure of the activity itself (Çoruh, 2013). As a social creature, man's type of relation and connection to the society he lives in directly affects his perception of himself and his formation to wholeness with his environment (Çulha, 1987). Behaviors gained and improved in this process of socialization affects whole life of an individual. Social behaviors formed by planned and programmed recreational activities contribute people's life satisfaction, wellness, self-esteem and self-confidence and thus make recreation as a service more than an activity.

Latest communication technologies provide a new media with opportunity to share individual's thoughts and creations gathered around the aim of sharing and discussion. This virtual platform called as social media takes an important role of uniting people and increasing the interaction between them (Vural & Bat, 2010). Kalafatoğlu (2011) defines social media as online, improvable, interactive, and connective communication channels which have groups within and participated by intended population. Weber (2009) defines social media as online places where people with common interests share their thoughts and comments. According to Goeldner and Ritchie (2011), online contents created by internet users rather than professional writers or journalists and delivered by interactive technology to other users form social media. Hatipoğlu (2009) called social media to a platform where people communicate with writings, photos, videos and voice files. Likewise Eröz and Doğdubay (2013) define

social media as social platforms where social media users share information, experiences, interests through the internet or mobile systems.

According to Dryer (2010) some successful social media, social networking sites and multimedia sharing sites made a revolutionary change and gave the opportunity of sharing and organizing information to ordinary people. A social networking site Facebook which is currently at top of these revolutionary sites and has the most user count around the World was launched in 2004 by Harvard student Mark Zuckerberg. At first the site was just open for Harvard students but in a short period it expanded to other college campuses, then high schools, businesses and by 2006 it was open to everyone (Boyd ve Ellison, 2008). Just after 12 years of launching this social networking site is located as the most visited social networking site all around the World (<http://www.alex.com/topsites>).

Popular and important social media sites can be in relation with each other. For example, it is possible to share a YouTube video on Facebook In a similar way a user's photo shared on Instagram can simultaneously be shared on Twitter. It is possible to say that applications support each other and grow even bigger together. In order to understand the importance of social media it is enough just to know the most three visited sites on internet two of which are social media sites. The development of methods and analysis on this significant and interrelated structure may give an opportunity to use this structure with control.

Considering the literature, some studies can be found about university students' recreational activities in Turkey (Sabbag & Aksoy, 2011; Demirel & Harmandar, 2009; Balci & İlhan, 2006; Müderisoğlu & Uzun 2004; Önder, 2003; Mansuroğlu, 2002). But any study about social media and its effect on recreation could not be found. Considering the growth rate of social media, it is important to study in this area also within the recreation context. Some studies suggest that usage of social media can manipulate individuals either positive or negative ways (Kramer et al., 2014) Because of this it can be thought that the same manipulation can be on individual's recreation tendencies. Therefore, it is important to clarify whether there is an effect of social media on these tendencies.

The time spent on social media is usually the time individuals reserved for themselves. In this free time, people interact with each other using their social media accounts. For this reason, using social media also creates 'a virtual socialness'. In this aspect, when identifying the effect of social media usage on recreational tendencies, also we are identifying tendencies afterwards 'a virtual socialness'.

Material and Methods

The students studying at sports in higher education in Turkey are the population of this study as 379 students studying at Trakya University Kırkpınar School of Physical Education and Sports in Edirne are the research sample. The study was conducted with the approval of Trakya University Social and Human Sciences Ethical Committee. Also, this study is driven from first author's master thesis.

The questionnaire used in this survey consists of three sections. In the first section, there are six questions meant to identify the demographic factors which are age, sex, department, active social media accounts and the time spent on social media. As social media, Facebook which has the most user count was preferred and in the second section, there are five questions about Facebook usage. Facebook questions are prepared based on Facebook Intensity Scale developed by Elisson, Steinfield and Lampe (2007). At the final section of the questionnaire, there are 17 questions to identify active recreation tendencies. These final questions are prepared based on Recreational Exercise Motivation Measure (REMM) developed by Rogers and Morris (2003) and its Turkish validity and reliability made by Gürbüz, Aşçı ve Çelebi (2006).

The data maintained through the questionnaire are analyzed and evaluated by SPSS 20.0. For participants socio-demographic structure descriptive statistics were used. Also, the questionnaire about recreation tendencies was factor analyzed and three dimensions were obtained. Mann Whittney U and Kruskal Wallis tests were used to examine the differences on social, physical and psychological dimensions according to socio-demographic factors.

Results and Discussion

In this study, social media's effect on active recreation tendencies was examined. In this context, in order to find this effect, a questionnaire was applied to social media using participants after a literature review and empirical study was conducted. 379 participants who study at sports in higher education joined this survey.

Participants' socio-demographic factors and the amount of time they spent on social media are given on Table 1.

Table 1: Socio-demographics of participants and the amount of time they spent on social media

	Variables	Frequency	% Frequency
	Age	17-21	259
22-26		111	29,3
27-31		9	2,4
Sex	Male	225	59,4
	Female	154	40,6
Department	Physical Education and Sports Teaching	63	16,6
	Coaching Education	178	47
	Sport Management	121	31,9
	Recreation	17	4,5
Time spent on Facebook	Less than 30 minutes	54	14,2
	30-60 minutes	167	44,1
	60-90 minutes	5	1,3
	More than 90 minutes	153	40,4

A total of 379 students participated to this survey with a female-male ratio of 40,6-59,4. 68,3% of students are aged between 17-21, 29,3% are aged between 22-26, and a few, 2,4% are aged between 27-31.

The distribution according to departments participants studying at is with 16,6% Physical Education and Sports Teaching, 47% Coaching Education, 31,9% Sport Management and finally with 4,5% Recreation. Moreover, 14,2% reported they spend on average less than 30 minutes, 44,1% 30-60 minutes, 1,3% 60-90 minutes and 40,4% more than 90 minutes in a day on their Facebook pages.

Table 2: Aim of Social Media Usage

Distribution of Facebook Usage Aims	Responses	
	N	Percent
Health	22	4,7
Competition	5	1,1
Body and Outer View	15	3,2
Social and Fun	344	73,8
Ability Improvement	19	4,1
Education	61	13,1
Total	466	100

From total 379 of participant, 359 of them answered the question about aim of social media usage. The reason of the count is 466, because a person can use social media for more than one reason.

As seen on Table 2 with 73,8% usage of Facebook for social reasons is far forward from others. The other reasons don't have significant percentages as Facebook. For 5

point Likert Scale's reliability analysis Cronbach Alpha Coefficient Method was used and the value of validity was found $\alpha=0,878$. According to this alpha coefficient method, the questionnaire found reliable.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test was used to determine whether the questionnaire of tendency is appropriate for factor analysis. The value of this test result was found 0,892. This result is a well found result for KMO test and shows that the data is appropriate for factor analysis. Because of the result of Barlett's test of sphericity is $p<0,005$ the variables are also appropriate for factor analysis and the total variance are given on Table 3.

Table 3: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6,226	36,626	36,626	6,226	36,626	36,626	3,783	22,253	22,253
2	2,730	16,057	52,683	2,730	16,057	52,683	3,392	19,951	42,203
3	1,267	7,453	60,136	1,267	7,453	60,136	3,049	17,932	60,136

As seen in Table, 3 dimensions are obtained from Recreation Tendency Scale. The factors' distribution in scale can be seen in the next table. According to Table 3, initial eigenvalues obtained from factor components are in order of 6,226, 2,730 ve 1,267. As to these values, factor distribution is appropriate.

In the same table, the value of total variance explained is 60,136. Therefore, the 3 factors explain 60,136% of total variance and it is accepted as statistically sufficient.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix

	Component		
	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
ES4	.742	.222	.054
ES3	.741	.219	-.033
ES15	.732	.077	.218
ES10	.708	.296	.037
ES17	.697	.250	.135
ES5	.605	.381	.027
ES7	.243	.814	.138
ES8	.204	.809	.114
ES12	.212	.752	.095
ES2	.304	.621	.126
ES11	.510	.616	.036
ES6	.513	.529	-.001
ES14	.126	-.021	.826
ES9	-.027	.201	.768
ES13	.030	.016	.758
ES1	.081	.089	.753
ES16	.100	.126	.711

The distribution of 3 dimensions are highlighted with dark color in table above. In this survey the 3 dimensions according to the factor analysis are:

- Factor 1: Physical Tendency;
- Factor 2: Psychological Tendency;
- Factor 3: Social Tendency.

The results examined with Mann Whitney U and Kruskal Wallis tests to find the differences of recreation tendencies scale's sub dimensions according to socio-demographic structure and the time spent on social media are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Sub-dimensions' Significance Levels of Recreation Tendencies Scale Relating to Socio-Demographic Structure and Time Spent on Social Media

Variable	Test	Physical Tendency	Psychological Tendency	Social Tendency
Sex	Mann Whitney U	0,12	,000	,523
Age	Kruskal Wallis	,753	,253	,573
Department	Kruskal Wallis	,253	,069	,024
Time spent on Facebook	Kruskal Wallis	,365	,760	,045

As seen in Table 5, considering $p > 0,05$, there aren't any significant differences between physical, psychological and social tendency dimensions according to age.

Because of $p < 0,05$ a significant difference was found between sex and psychological tendency. Also in the same dimension, there is a significant difference between the departments which participants study and their sex. There are significant differences at social tendency dimension also according to the departments which participants study at and the time they spent in social media.

As seen in Table 4 and 5, Recreational Tendency Scale was factor analyzed and 3 dimensions were obtained. Mann Whitney U and Kruskal Wallis Tests were used to test whether participants have attitude differences at these sub-dimensions. At physical tendency dimension as first dimension there aren't any significant differences found according to age, sex, department and the time spent on social media.

At second dimension as psychological dimension, from all socio-demographic factors, only a significant difference was found between their sex according to the test results. The results showed that women participants have more sensitivity to psychological dimension of recreation tendency scale. Because of this result, it is suggested that psychologically women have more tendencies to active recreational activities.

As the third dimension of recreation tendencies at social tendency dimension, it is found that participants have differences according to the departments they study and the time they spent on social media. According to Mann Whitney U test to define the reason of the difference for department they study, it is found that student's studies at sport management department have more social tendencies to active recreation than other departments. As for the time spent on social media, it was found that students spending more than 91 minutes have more social tendencies than others. Thus, it is possible to say that students spending more time on social media have more social outcomes.

The study about self-worth and Facebook usage shows that when usage of Facebook increases individual's self-worth and self-esteem decreases and it is more significant among women. Also, when the usage of Facebook increases, women's happiness level decreases and they find their life less satisfactory (Yıldırım, 2014, s.81). Because of this, it should be considered that social media does not have just positive impacts. Although the fact that social media has also negative effects, 52% of population in Turkey uses social media and 26% of them use Facebook. So with or without negative effect this platform should be investigated in many ways including recreation tendencies.

Recreational activities improve individual's' life quality and provide some physical, social and psychological benefits to individuals (Zorba, 2014; Çoruh, 2013; Roque ve Verissimo, 2011). Participation to re-creation activities give an opportunity to develop primarily to individual himself then to the society (Erkal vd., 1998).

The results at the study made by Kuo and Tang (2014) about Facebook usage, personality characteristics and leisure attitudes (2014) are likely to the results obtained in this survey. Both studies support that individuals use social media with an aim to socialize. In this case, it is asserted that also as creating an active tendency to recreational activity, Facebook is also a passive social recreation activity itself.

The test results about the time spent on social media showed that when people spend more time on social media their social tendencies to active recreation activities increase. In Kuo ve Tang's (2014) study a positive relation was mentioned about the time spent at social media and leisure time attitudes. Therefore supporting Kuo & Tang (2014) it is argued that increasing social media usage increases social tendencies to recreation activities. Due to the growth of social media the increasing usage of it, is almost inevitable. Thus, the recreational activities should be managed and planned by taking the importance of answering the need to socialize into consideration.

Recommendations

It is known that social networks have security flaws. Especially nowadays, there are some major problems about information security. The recreational service organizations' prior responsibility should be the security of their users' personal information. The providers of these social media services should cooperate for international information security and ensure its security and reliability.

It is important to exist in a platform where most of university students spend at least 30 minutes per day. Organizations which provide recreation services need social media accounts especially on Facebook, Instagram, YouTube and Twitter. Social media usage increases social tendency to recreational activities. When considered the growth of social media recreational activities need to be planned and programmed to answer these existing and ever increasing social tendencies. Also while planning recreation activities for an increased participation of women; the highlight should be on psychological benefits of recreation activities.

The organizations and foundations providing recreational service should use social media as a tool, and they should use this tool for the awareness of their services. For example, Sport for All Federation in Turkey has several social media accounts and by these accounts, this federation is trying to raise the awareness of physical fitness. If these kinds of organizations and foundations use their accounts considering the gained social tendency and plan their marketing actions in this context, they will be able to activate people for joining recreational activity rather than promoting existing social tendencies passively.

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